

Retention of aldrin in soil

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Soil-inhabiting gryllids *Brachytrypes portentosus* and *Gryllotalpa africana* frequently pose a problem to direct-seeded upland rice in northern West Bengal. The infestation is generally prevented by the application of 5% aldrin dust. Aldrin, one of the most persistent cyclodiene insecticides, is being phased out, however.

Aldrin disappears from European and American soils in approximately 3 years on the average. In terai soils of Jalpaiguri district in North Bengal, its bioactivity rapidly wanes and insect reinfestation occurs within about 5 months after application. An experiment on the retention of aldrin in sandy loam and alluvial soils was therefore conducted.

To study the soil retention of aldrin a copper cylinder 23.1 cm high and 7 cm in diameter with 1 outlet through a short spout in the bottom was used. Filter paper was wrapped around a perforated

Residue of aldrin in 2 different soils (mean of 3 samples) of Jalpaiguri district, northernwest Bengal, India.

Soil type	Aldrin recovered (ppm) when leached with				Control (ppm)
	153.24 mm water	229.86 mm water	510.80 mm water	1532.40 mm water	
Terai (sandy loam)	26	22	12	5	36
Alluvium (silty loam)	22	16	2	1	35

copper disc that just fitted the bottom of the cylinder. Two grams of fresh 5% aldrin dust of 75 µm particle size was thoroughly mixed with 2.4 kg of each air-dried soil type. Then 800 g samples were placed in copper cylinders and lightly compacted, making the soil column 14.22 cm high. The cylinders were then clamped to a stand.

Next 97.8 ml distilled water was percolated through the soil columns in installments. Soil in a control cylinder received no water. After the experiments, the soils were collected from the cylinders, air-dried, and analyzed for residue by gas liquid chromatography at the Indian Agricultural Research Institute, New Delhi. The results are in the table.

Aldrin is substantially displaced or inactivated in both soil types. The

reduction, however, is most appreciable in the sandy loam soil, which contains more organic matter (mostly undecomposed). Possibly because of rapid aldrin reduction, reinfestation by soil insects occurs.

Invitation to authors

The International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) invites all scientists to contribute concise summaries of significant rice research for publication. Contributions should be limited to one or two paragraphs and a table, figure, or photograph. They are subject to editing and abridgement to meet space limitations. Authors will be identified by name, title, and research organization.

Pest management and control

WEEDS

Weed management studies on direct-seeded and transplanted rice in 1976 aus in Bangladesh

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A study was begun in 1976 to compare the effectiveness of herbicides with that of hand weeding to identify weed differences between plots of short-statured and of taller local varieties and to determine the weed-caused yield reduction in direct-seeded and transplanted rice.

BR3 – a short-statured, high yielding rice variety – and Dhariāl – a tall local variety – were direct-seeded in rows into dry soil 13 April. Thirty-day-old seedlings

Yield of BR3 and Dhariāl rice under various weed management practices in the 1976 aus season, Dacca, Bangladesh.

Treatment	Herbicide rate ^a (kg a.i./ha)	Yield ^b (t/ha)					
		Direct seeded			Transplanted		
		BR3	Dhariāl	Mean	BR3	Dhariāl	Mean
Butachlor							
+ hand weeding	0.5	5.99	3.04	4.52 a	6.68	1.49	4.09 a
Hand weeding	–	5.69	2.45	4.01 ab	6.43	1.45	3.94 ab
Butachlor	1.5	4.11	2.05	3.38 b	6.09	1.39	3.14 b
Thiobencarb	1.5	4.44	2.49	3.46 b	5.99	1.39	3.69 b
Piperophos/ dimethametryn	1.2/0.3	4.12	1.91	3.55 b	5.91	1.36	3.66 b
Control	–	3.25	1.32	2.30 c	5.95	1.36	3.66 b
Av.		4.80 b	2.22 c	3.52	6.19 a	1.41 d	3.79

^a Applied 3 days after seeding.

^b Any two means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

were transplanted 4 May in rows 20 × 20 cm apart. Herbicides for six weed control treatments (see table) were

applied 3 days after seeding and were activated by irrigating the plots. The recommended levels of cultural practices

and fertilizer were followed. Rice yield, weed species, and weed weights were determined at harvest.

Results are shown in the table. Whether direct-seeded or transplanted, the high yielding variety BR3 outyielded the local variety. When transplanted, it produced 31% more yield than when direct-seeded. The local variety had lower yields because of its low tillering rate when transplanted; however, it yielded 40% more when direct-seeded.

Weeds were a problem in the direct-seeded plots. The control plot had significantly lower yields, 39% less than the herbicide-treated and hand-weeded

plots.

The best treatment combined a low dose of herbicide and hand weeding. Although the yield it gave did not differ significantly from that of hand weeding, it was better than that of any of the three herbicide treatments. In Bangladesh, the combination of a low dose of herbicide and weeding would be practical and would complement the existing hand-weeding methods.

The transplanted plot had less weed infestation and showed no significant reduction in yield between the control and the herbicide-alone plots. A low dose of herbicide plus hand weeding, however,

increased yields by 9% over the control. The cultural practice of puddling plus the competitive advantage of the transplanted rice plant over weeds greatly reduced weed problems where water management was good.

The weed species present in the BR3 and Dharial plots differed. In BR3 the sedges *Cyperus iria*, *Cyperus difformis*, and *Fimbristylis littoralis* were the major weeds. In the plots of the taller Dharial, sedge growth was much reduced, and the grass *Echinochloa crus-galli* was the dominant weed. Weed weights in the Dharial direct-seeded control plots were 92 g/m² compared with 133 g/m² in BR3.

Soil and crop management

Residual effect of blue-green algae application on rice yield

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Field trials to determine the residual effect of blue-green algae for nitrogen fixation on rice yields were laid out using ADT31 during the 1975 and 1976 kar (July–Oct.) season and using IR20 during the 1975 and 1976 pishanam (Nov.–March) season. The treatments were 50–25–25 kg NPK/ha, 50–25–25 kg NPK/ha plus 10 kg algae/ha, 25–25–25 kg NPK/ha, 25–25–25 kg/ha plus 10 kg algae/ha, algae alone at 10 kg/ha, and the untreated control.

After four seasons, the same treatments were repeated during the 1977 kar and 1977–78 pishanam seasons, with no algae added. Withholding algae did not generally affect the yield trend much (see table). In the plots where algae alone were applied, however, yields decreased slightly in the 1977 kar season. The results indicate that the residual effects of application of blue-green algae for a continuous period of four seasons will provide sufficient inoculum for subsequent crops.

Effect of blue-green algae on rice yields, Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment	1977 kar season ^a		1977–78 pishanam season ^b	
	Yield (t/ha)	Increase or decrease over control (%)	Yield (t/ha)	Increase or decrease over control (%)
0 NPK	3.3	–	4.8	–
0 NPK +blue-green algae	3.2	3.2	5.4	13.9
25–25–25 kg NPK/ha	3.3	2.2	5.2	7.6
25–25–25 kg NPK/ha + blue-green algae	3.8	17.1	5.2	9.8
50–25–25 kg NPK/ha	3.8	11.2	5.1	7.6
50–25–25 kg NPK/ha + 10 kg/ha blue-green algae	4.1	24.6	5.1	7.6
F test:	S		NS	
CD:	456		–	

^aJuly–October. ^bNovember–March.

Fertilizers for deep placement and slow release of nitrogen for rice

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Rice commonly uses only 30 to 40% of applied fertilizer nitrogen. A great deal of research has therefore been carried out to develop more efficient nitrogen fertilizer sources and management

practices.

Three major approaches that have been developed are split application, deep placement, and controlled release. The latter two approaches — as mudballs or urea supergranules and sulfur-coated urea, respectively — have frequently proven superior to split application of urea in experiments conducted in the 10 countries of the International Network on Fertilizer Efficiency in Rice.

A fourth approach combines the deep placement and slow-release concepts. A